

Synthesis and characterization of nano lead oxide gas sensors

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Abstract : Lead oxide sample was prepared at low temperature by the solvo-thermal method. The lead oxide characterized by X-Ray diffraction (XRD), transmission electron spectroscopy (TEM) were employed to identify the structural phases and particle size. X-Ray diffraction and transmission electron microscopic studies confirms the nanocrystalline nanoparticles. This lead oxide were used to fabricate volatile organic gas sensors. The effect of temperature and transient characteristics for various VOCs (butanol, ethanol, propanol and methanol) are reported.

Keywords : Nanoparticle, lead oxide, characterization, gas response.

Introduction

Alcohols are used as industrial solvents in the industry. Exposing to these solvents to human beings and living things are hazardous which necessities to monitors its presence in the environment continuously. Late it has opened up new area of alcohol sensors. A wide range of metal oxides have been used in gas sensors, including Fe_2O_3 , CuO , NiO , TiO_2 , ZnO , SnO_2 and WO_3 ¹⁻³. Traditional and commercial gas sensors are based on thick or thin films of *n*-type semiconducting metal oxide SnO_2 those have low sensitivity and high power consumption, rendering them difficult to actual applications⁴. Therefore, nowadays, researchers are trying to find more suitable materials and/or special structures for better gas sensors with higher stability, higher sensitivity, and greater selectivity⁵. Among others, materials with nanostructures, such as nanoparticles⁶, nanorods⁷, nanowires⁸ and nanotubes⁹ have been attracting scientists' attention worldwide because of their advanced physical and chemical properties as well as their many applications, including of chemical and gas sensors¹⁰.

In gas-sensing applications, the small size and large surface area-to-volume ratio of nanomaterials are required to improve the sensing sites for better performance. In particular, one-dimensional (1D) materials like nanotubes¹¹, nanorods¹² and nanowires¹³ have reportedly shown high sensitivity in gas-sensor applications due to

their high surface area-to-volume ratio and other unique properties. Of these resistive sensors are frequently employed because of its simplicity.

Lead oxide (PbO) has been used as a recyclable catalyst, with excellent results, in one pot synthesis of quinoxalines¹⁴. Of the available methods, precipitation, hydrothermal and solvo-thermal methods have gained importance due to the fact that they are simple, employ low synthesis temperature and ensure pure single and multi products.

Among them, solvo-thermal synthesis has been a major focus in the preparative investigations due to the advantages over other techniques, such as low-cost, mild temperature, potential controllability over size and morphology, which play key roles in tailoring the properties of nanomaterials. Sensing mechanisms were explained to gain a better understanding.

Not much work has been reported on lead oxide alcohol sensors to the best of our knowledge. The present study report results of preparation, characterization nano lead oxide sensor for alcohols.

Experimental

The PbO was prepared by dissolving lead acetate in isopropanol at room temperature and stirred continuously until a clear transparent solution is obtained. The solution is then adjusted to pH 9 by adding 1 N NaOH which

results in the formation of a dense precipitate and this is thoroughly stirred using a magnetic stirrer for about 10 h at 75 °C. This precipitate is then filtered and washed with double distilled water followed by drying in a hot air oven at 75 °C to yield PbO which is labeled as PBIS75. The as-synthesized powder was grounded and made in the form of paste and coated on the hollow alumina tube. The cylindrical coated alumina tube was dried for 1 h and then heat treated at 100 °C for 30 min in a hot air oven.

Results and discussion

X-Ray diffraction studies :

The XRD patterns of the as-synthesized PbO sample at 75 °C and heat treated samples are shown in Fig. 1. The sample prepared at 75 °C showed a pure form of stable α -PbO. The reflections peaks well indexed to the standard pattern of α -PbO (JCPDS Card No. 85-1739). The average crystallite size calculated from Scherrer formula using the (002) diffraction peaks for PBIS75, 92 nm indicating that the PbO formed particle is made of nanocrystallite.

The magnified TEM image (insert) also reveals that the PbO nanoparticles are loose. The inserted selected area electron diffraction (SAED) pattern in Fig. 1 further proves the polycrystalline nature of the α -PbO nanoparticles.

VOC sensing measurements :

Fig. 1. XRD pattern of PbO.

Sensing measurement :

The as-prepared powder obtained by the above method was first ground using a mortar and pestle to achieve consistent and fine particles and was taken and mixed with distilled water. The paste was coated onto an alumina substrate between electrical contacts to obtain a thick film.

The electrical resistance of sample was measured for varying concentration of gas in air. After each exposure, the test chamber was purged with air. Sensitivity (S) is defined as the change in resistance in the presence of the gas normalized to the value of resistance obtained in air, and is given by

$$S = \frac{R_g - R_a}{R_g} \quad (1)$$

where R_{gas} and R_{air} are the dc resistance values of the sensor under gas exposure and in dry air, respectively.

After placing a fabricated sensor in the test chamber, measured quantity of solvent was injected into the test chamber. A dc power supply and a Keithely 614 digital electrometer were connected to the metallic contacts of the coated alumina substrate through the chamber. Sensing characteristics of the sample was obtained through I - V measurements towards a variety of alcohol sensing solvents such as butanol, propanol, ethanol and methanol of AR grade. The heater inlet of such vapors to the measuring chamber was controlled by a micro-syringe.

For the detection of alcohol solvents vapors with the lead oxide based sensor element, it is well known that chemisorbed oxygen at PbO surfaces plays an important role. As a result of chemisorptions there can appear O^{2-} , O_2^- and O^- ions depending on the temperature at the surface. According to Kohl¹⁵ O^{2-} species are highly unstable and do not play much role in determining the sensitivity. Thus, the major adsorbed species that influences the sensitivity of a sensor element might be O^- . This adsorbed oxygen creates a space charge region near the coated surface by extracting electrons from the material.

The maximum sensitivity temperature for alcohol solvents (butanol, propanol, ethanol and methanol) varies with the material. It is shown that at the maximum operating temperature most of the adsorbed oxygen species would have reacted with alcohol vapor. This adsorbed

Fig. 2. Temperature dependence of gas response of PbO and concentration of various alcohols (insert).

oxygen creates a space charge region near the surface of the material by extracting electrons from the material. Alcohol, reducing in nature, removes adsorbed oxygen species from the surface and re-injects the electrons back to the material, thereby decreasing the resistance. The maximum sensitivity at the respective maximum working temperature indicates that the equilibrium density of chemisorbed oxygen ions is maximum at this temperature. From the results, it was observed that the sensitivity decreases after heat treatment of α -PbO (mono phase) because of increase in particle size and reduction in the surface area. This is a good agreement with the TEM analysis.

Transient characteristics :

Fig. 3 gives the transient characteristics of α -PbO at temperature corresponds to maximum sensitivity. The

Fig. 3. Transient characteristics of PbO.

following figure show the log R as a function of time and it was found to quicker respond and recovery to be 14 and 8 s respectively.

Conclusion

In summary, α -PbO nanoparticles (about 90 nm) have been successfully obtained by a simple one-step solid state reaction. Sensitivities studies for reducing gases is carried out to demonstrate that this lead oxide highly sensitive to butanol. The good response and recovery properties of this material also enable to be used as a good gas sensor material. This technique can be used for the detection of a variety of solvents and by adding different dopant to the material the sensitivity of the lead oxide can be increased. This work under progress.

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